

**THE NEW WAYS TO EXPAND POPULARITY OF ENGLISH AND MODERN
METHODS IN SCHOOLS AND LYCEUMS.**

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Abstract. *This article is devoted to the needs of new methods to make English more popular among new growing number of children who are owners of our future. Also discusses the new ways to expand popularity of English among learners and students. Moreover, it provides with the new methods of teaching English via Multimedia technologies.*

Keywords: *methods, modern technologies, internet, multimedia, teaching skills.*

Аннотация. *Данная статья посвящена потребностям новых методик популяризации английского языка среди растущего числа детей, которые являются хозяевами нашего будущего. Также обсуждаются новые способы повышения популярности английского языка среди учащихся и студентов. Кроме того, он предоставляет новые методы обучения английскому языку с помощью мультимедийных технологий.*

Ключевые слова: *методика, современные технологии, Интернет, мультимедиа, педагогическое мастерство.*

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqola kelajagimiz egalari bo'lgan yangi o'sib borayotgan yoshlar orasida ingliz tilini yanada ommalashtirish uchun yangi usullarning ehtiyojlariga bag'ishlangan. Shuningdek, ingliz tilini o'rganuvchilar va talabalar orasida ingliz tilining ommaviyligini oshirishning yangi usullari haqida so'z boradi. Bundan tashqari, ingliz tilini Multimedia texnologiyalari orqali o'qitishning yangi usullari bilan ta'minlangan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *metodlar, zamonaviy texnologiyalar, internet, multimedia, o'qitish ko'nikmalari.*

Introduction.

First and foremost, there are currently about 6,500 languages around the world, but as we know, the most well-known one is English. Because almost every international trade, every international political issue is held by this language. Historically, the world after the first and second world wars was a vulnerable and changing one. American businesses were booming and started doing trade all over the world, much like Great Britain had done in the previous century. This bolstered the use of English as the language of global trade. That can be the main reason why all countries are learning English as their second language. So, if English is such worldwide, how can we learn it? Or how can we treat it as our second mother tongue? I guess, to reach these things, we need to raise new generation with better knowledge towards languages and provide them with solid mindset with the use of teachers' professional work.

There was organized many events in Uzbekistan for the development of other languages by the first President of Uzbekistan Islom Karimov's decision about improving the system of learning international languages on the 10th of December 2012. It was the proof, that language-developing works have already been started in Uzbekistan. Furthermore, current President Shavkat Miromonovich Mirziyoyev has also added his share for the improvement of international languages. For example, on the 6th of May there was a video selector carried out about improving teaching international languages in Uzbekistan. Sh. M. Mirziyoyev said, that the time has come to

establish a new system for teaching foreign languages in our country, which will be a solid foundation for the future. Since, we have set the goal of building a competitive country, and now graduates of schools, lyceums, colleges and universities must know at least two foreign languages perfectly. Strict demand should become the main criteria for the activity of the head of every educational institution. In my opinion, it is high time now to educate people, especially kids to their second language. Because after so many events, so many works that are being carried out nowadays, it is very hard not to learn other languages. There is great respect and attention towards them in our people. [4]

These days, the number of library lovers in Uzbekistan is increased a lot, compared to 2 or 3 years ago. The reason can be for this, I think, that there are new technologies, computers, as well as new facilities in every library around the country. The readers can take any information or material he or she wants. For example, if he or she cannot find the information that they are searching for in books, they can easily put it on the internet, and it helps them immediately providing with lots of information. All I am going to say is that now, there is a massive advantage to learn everything.

Moreover, teachers' skills and their knowledge are also one of the most important things in the improvement of child's language-learning process. There is a reason why only the teachers who have solid knowledge and educating skills can provide learners with unlimited education. At the moment, in Uzbekistan, different classes are being set up by the government for teachers to aid them increase their level and help them to become professional in their field. For example, English-teaching teachers are going to universities in other regions around the country in every 5 years to strengthen their language. Furthermore, the decision of the head of state "On measures to support public education scientific-research services and introduction of professional development" PQ-4963 on the radical renewal of qualification control is introducing a new procedure in the field. That is, the current regulation, public education, and also, the involvement of teachers in training courses in every 5 years. Now they will be able to improve their qualification level not once in every 5 years, but each year. [1]

For this purpose, "continuing professional education" is introduced, taking into account the qualification of public education every year. According to the previous procedure, only 20 teachers were involved in the auxiliary qualification every year, but according to the new procedure, 100% of the teachers were involved in the qualification every year. Previously, 144 hours were taught in qualification courses once in every 5 years, but according to the new rules, teachers should be involved in at least 36 hours of studies per year.[2]

To effectively conduct an English class at a non-linguistic university and successfully achieve maximum results, students and teachers in their practice use a variety of methods, techniques and technologies, improving their professional competencies and personal qualities. Among modern teaching technologies, the most in demand are: information and communication technologies (ICT), technologies for the use of computer programs, Internet technologies, personality-oriented technologies, language portfolio technology, technologies testing, design technologies, collaborative learning technologies, gaming technologies, critical thinking development technologies, communication and value technologies. [5, p129]

Multimedia technologies, being the field of information technologies, are a complex of modern means of audio-television and virtual communications, which are used for various activities: planning, organization, control in various fields: medicine, advertising, art, business,

scientific research, entertainment and education. Multimedia (English "multimedia" from Latin "multum" - a lot and "media", "medium" - focus; means) is an electronic carrier of multiple media that create different types of information (text, sound, graphics, video, photo, animations, sound effects (noise, creak, rain, thunder, etc.) that interact with each other. The interaction of visual and sound information is controlled by interactive software. One of the main advantages of using multimedia tools is that they allow you to organize a variety of learning activities for students, providing various ways to expand vocabulary and get acquainted with new patterns of statements, improve the memorability of the structures being studied. Language and relationships between these structures, training certain skills and abilities. One of the advantages of using multimedia tools is also the fact that they contribute to the optimization of the system of control and self-control, thereby facilitating the work of the teacher, as well as developing the independence of students. Thanks to the use of computer tests, students get the opportunity to independently control the degree of assimilation of the studied material and, if necessary, repeat it. It should also be emphasized that for each multimedia program, a methodological note should be drawn up, which indicates what audience the program is designed for, the types of skills that are developed with its help, what educational material it is based on, how many hours it is designed for, the place of this programs in the educational process, that is, "the program must have a use case for the possibility of using it by other teachers". [5, p130]

In addition, in order to educate pupils, teachers need to obey following rules:

- Make It Fun

Fun, fun, fun! This is one factor that really matters to kids. And that goes for kids on the playground as well as those in the classroom.

- Play Games

Games are a great way to make learning fun. Not only do games play on the competitive nature of most children, but games also give them a goal to accomplish. When you win a game, you have really done something, and you can feel good about your success.

- Be Creative

Doing the same things in class every day is boring for the students, and you're liable to fall asleep on the job, too. So, you need to be creative with plans.[3]

Conclusion

To conclude, in this developing world, it is very beneficial to learn international languages especially the most popular one English, because it can lighten your way wherever you are, as well as, there is always a high demand for teachers that are professional in their job. For being professional in our country provides a huge number of works, like providing with wide range of sources and possibilities. Teachers are working on new ways of teaching English as a second language and new modern methods, integrating multimedia technologies.

In addition, if the new growing generation have much information and knowledge about life, culture, economy or language of different countries, we can totally be sure, that our country is in trustful hands.

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